

Table 1. Performance of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V in research station observational yield trials. Cameroon, 1987 and 1988.

Variety or line	Grain yield ^a		Duration (d)	Reaction ^b to		Panicle exertion ^b
	(t/ha)			Sheath rot	Grain discoloration	
	1987	1988				
Tainan V	4.3	3.3	150	5	5	3
IR7167-33-2-3	5.5	4.4	142	3	3	3

^aMean of 6 trials/year. ^bStandard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale.

NPK/ha. The farmers' field trials were conducted according to normal farmer practices.

IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan V in 1987 and 1988 trials at the Bamunka research site (Table 1). In 1988 on-

station trials, IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan V by an average 36%. IR7167-33-2-3 also showed greater resistance to ShR and GID.

In farmers' fields in the Bamunka area, IR7167-33-2-3 outyielded Tainan

Table 2. Yields of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V in farmers' fields at Ndop Plain, Cameroon.

Variety or line	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	
	1987	1988
Tainan V	3.4	3.2
IR7167-33-2-3	4.9	4.5

^aMean of 6 farms sampled/year.

V on all six farms sampled in 1987 (Table 2). Yield trends were similar in 1988.

IR7167-33-2-3 has an average yield advantage over Tainan V of 32% on station and 45% in farmers' fields. □

ASD17, a short-duration red rice variety for tail end irrigation areas of Tambiraparani Delta and Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu

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Short-duration red rice culture AS688, isolated from the double cross derivative of ADT31/Ratna//ASD8/IR8, has been released as rice variety ASD17 for

cultivation in tail end irrigation areas of Tambiraparani tract and Kanyakumari District. It is suitable for cultivation during kannipoo season (Apr-Jul) in Kanyakumari and kar season (Jun-Sep) and late pishanam season (Nov-Feb) in Nellai Kattabomman District. ASD17 can replace local varieties Kuruvai, Arupatham kuruvai, and Annapoorna in Kanyakumari and Thuyamalli in Nellai Kattabomman.

ASD17 is 96 cm tall and matures in 100 d. Mean grain yield was 5.4 t/ha over 10 yr in 27 different trials (see table). Mean straw yield was 9.0 t/ha.

Early senescence is its distinguishing character. The variety produces its maximum grain yield when younger

seedlings (18-20 d) are transplanted. Grain is short and bold red rice, with high consumer preference.

ASD17 has field tolerance for tungro and blast and moderate resistance to brown planthopper and sheath rot. □

Performance of some improved rice varieties under irrigated and rainfed lowland conditions at Parwanipur, Nepal

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We studied yield and yield attributes and some agronomic traits of 10 released and 1 prerelease variety under irrigated and rainfed lowland conditions in 1988 wet season (May-Oct).

The experiments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Seeds were sown on dry seedbed on 26 May for irrigated rice and 7 Jun for rainfed lowland. Seedlings were transplanted at 1 seedling/hill, 25 × 25cm row spacing, 30 d after sowing. Fertilizer was applied at 80-20-20 kg NPK/ha. Plots were protected against weeds, insect pests, and diseases. Net area harvested was 5.0 m²/plot.

Filled grains were separated from unfilled grains using Dockaging

Performance of ASD17 in Tamil Nadu.

Trial	Trials (no.)	% increase				
		TKM9	ASD8	Cauvery	Arupatham kuruvai	Anna-poorna
Rice Research Station, Ambasamudram, 1979-88	27	6.8	—	—	—	—
Adaptive Research Trials, Kanyakumari District, 1981 wet season	10	2.6	—	—	—	—
1981 semidry season	7	6.1	—	—	—	—
1984 and 1987	15	—	—	—	1.8	—
1988	20	—	—	—	—	7.4
Adaptive Research Trials, Tirunelveli District, 1987 and 1988	34	—	37.3	—	—	—
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, 1981 direct seeded rainfed	9	—	—	7.7	—	—
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, 1981 direct seeded irrigated	2	—	—	1.7	—	—
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, 1981 transplanted	9	—	—	10.1	—	—

Table 1. Pooled analysis of yield components of 11 rice varieties under irrigated (I) and rainfed lowland (R) conditions at Parwanipur, Nepal, 1988 wet season.

Variety	Productive tillers at harvest (no.)			Filled grains/panicle (no.)			% unfilled grains/panicle ^a			100-grain weight (g)		
	I	R	Mean	I	R	Mean	I	R	Mean	I	R	Mean
NR15016-2-4-1-3	31.3	38.4	34.9	247.27	258.6	252.93	11.04 (3.28)	6.59 (2.65)	8.81 (2.96)	1.95	1.92	1.93
CH45	47.7	66.7	57.2	73.0	62.6	67.8	4.68 (2.27)	7.31 (2.78)	5.99 (2.52)	2.46	2.57	2.51
Makawapur 1	39.0	52.7	45.8	119.54	124.6	122.07	8.58 (3.01)	7.22 (2.76)	7.9 (2.92)	2.52	2.59	2.55
Barkhe 2	48.0	65.0	55.5	104.07	119.0	115.53	9.26 (3.03)	5.88 (2.51)	7.57 (2.72)	1.77	1.96	1.86
Sabitri	45.0	57.0	51.0	120.34	125.2	122.77	7.97 (2.89)	8.63 (3.01)	8.3 (2.95)	2.07	1.97	2.02
Bindeswari	46.0	62.0	54.0	95.07	120.4	107.33	15.05 (3.91)	5.9 (2.51)	10.47 (3.21)	1.95	1.95	1.95
Mallika	35.0	55.3	45.2	123.34	141.0	132.17	18.28 (4.32)	6.04 (2.51)	12.16 (3.46)	2.0	2.1	2.05
Ghaiya 2	41.3	51.7	46.5	97.17	110.6	103.87	9.71 (3.16)	4.3 (2.17)	7.0 (2.66)	2.23	2.34	2.28
Chaite 4	55.3	51.3	53.3	60.87	88.4	74.63	21.89 (4.57)	11.25 (3.38)	16.57 (3.97)	2.32	2.32	2.32
Masuli	42.7	54.7	48.7	140.47	176.8	158.63	9.23 (3.04)	5.71 (2.48)	7.47 (2.76)	1.55	1.64	1.59
Janaki	32.0	47.4	39.7	87.07	143.0	115.0	8.37 (2.92)	6.9 (2.69)	7.63 (2.8)	2.52	2.65	2.58
Mean	42.1	54.7	48.0	115.28	133.69	124.0	11.28 (3.31)	6.88 (2.68)	9.08 (2.99)	2.12	2.18	2.14
F test ^b	**	*	**	**	**	**	ns	*	*	**	**	**
CV (%)	15.1	14.1	14.6	21.11	14.07	17.39	23.69	12.34	20.12	5.78	6.15	5.88
LSD (0.05)	4.4	5.3	2.4	16.91	13.07	7.5	—	0.22	0.2	0.08	0.08	0.27
Cultural type × genotype	—	—	ns	—	—	ns	—	—	ns	—	—	ns

^a Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{X+0.5}$ transformed values and LSD values refer to them. ^b** = significant at 0.01 probability, * = significant at 0.05 probability, ns = not significant.

Table 2. Pooled analysis of some agronomic traits of 11 rice varieties under irrigated (I) and rainfed lowland (R) conditions at Puwanipur, Nepal, 1988 wet season.

Variety	Plant height (cm)			Flowering (d after sowing)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	I	R	Mean	I	R	Mean	I	R	Mean
NR15016-24-1-3	141.8	142.4	142.2	120.33	119.0	119.66	2.8	3.6	3.2
CH45	124.73	110.6	117.66	88.0	81.3	84.65	2.4	2.7	2.5
Makawanpur 1	113.2	108.26	106.7	126.33	122.0	124.16	2.0	3.2	2.6
Barkhe 2	100.53	88.8	94.66	126.33	126.3	126.31	2.0	3.1	2.5
Sabitri	100.26	103.4	101.83	121.0	116.6	118.8	1.7	2.6	2.1
Bindeswari	104.13	104.0	104.04	96.0	94.0	95.0	2.5	3.0	2.8
Mallika	125.2	120.1	122.65	90.33	93.0	91.66	2.3	3.0	2.7
Ghaiya 2	91.93	89.9	90.91	84.33	89.0	86.66	2.1	3.0	2.5
Chaite 4	96.4	94.4	95.4	88.66	85.6	87.13	1.8	2.5	2.2
Masuli	134.2	127.9	131.05	122.0	125.3	123.65	2.4	3.6	3.0
Janaki	104.06	105.0	104.53	105.33	106.3	105.81	1.8	2.8	2.3
Mean	112.4	108.6	110.00	106.24	105.4	213.57	2.2	3.0	2.6
F test ^a	**	**	**	**	**	**	*	*	**
CV (%)	3.45	9.65	7.17	2.72	3.5	3.12	14.6	11.9	13.2
LSD (0.05)	2.96	7.13	2.73	2.00	2.5	1.14	0.2	0.2	0.08
Cultural type × genotype	—	—	ns	—	—	ns	—	—	ns

^a** = significant at 0.01 probability, * = significant at 0.05 probability, ns = not significant. Correlation between number of filled grains/panicle and no. of productive tillers at harvest ($r = -0.749^{**}$) ($n = 11$). Correlation between no. of filled grains/panicle and yield ($r = 0.744^{**}$) ($n = 11$). Correlation between plant height and yield ($r = 0.792^{**}$) ($n = 11$).

Machine. Yield attributes are presented in Table 1 and agronomic attributes in Table 2.

Yield and agronomic components are relatively better under rainfed lowland condition than under irrigated. That may be partly because of monocropping in rainfed lowland, with greater availability of micronutrients. This indicates that identification of improved varieties suitable for broad adaptability is possible. □

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MAU2159, a high-yielding glutinous rice for East China

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NAU2159, released in 1985, has proven to fit farmer demands for a high-yielding

Comparison of some traits of NAU2159 and its parents (1986).

Cultivar	Days to heading	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Seed set (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Protein content (%)	Amylose content (%)	Alkali spreading value	Gel consistency (mm)
Nanjing 11	92	98.1	24.0	152.6	79.8	26.7	13.00 ^a	27.8 ^a	6.2 ^a	30 ^a
NAU2159	96	101.3	24.0	166.3	82.1	27.4	9.41 ^c	2.4 ^c	6.0 ^c	103.5 ^c
IR29	96	87.4	18.9	77.8	89.2	22.8	8.00 ^b	0.0 ^b	6.2 ^b	99.0 ^b

^aFrom IRRI, 1982. ^bFrom IRRI, 1980. ^cFrom Hubei Academy of Agricultural Science, 1986.